

Review Article

User Education Programme: A Panacea for Effective Utilization of Library Resource

Onuoha, Aruabuiké Elija
Reader's Services Librarian, Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Osun State, Nigeria

Abstract

It is the library's responsibility to provide better services to its users to make sure that information resources, services and facilities are maximally utilized for users' benefits. Due to severed reasons and with the aim of providing timely services several artificial techniques are followed for the arrangement of materials, and for interpreting them to the users. To enable the users to know their rights in the library, to what extent they can get the benefit of the library services, a formal introduction of the library to a newcomer is essential. Hence, the library professionals should bring to the notice of its users all the resources, services and the facilities by conducting user education programme at regular interval in batches or individually, if necessary, so that they will become much familiar with various services, facilities and resource of the library with such kind of skill and knowledge, they will make use of library materials to a maximum extent. To a large extent the maximum utilization of library resources, service and facilities depend on effective teaching on user education.

Keywords: Information Resources, Library Skills, User Awareness, Libraries, Services, Facilities.

Introduction

Libraries, regardless of their types, have three basic functions viz: the collection and preservation of information, the organization of information and the dissemination of stored information to users. The library collections in whatever form either in print, non print, or electronic, are used for studying, teaching, research, and recreational purposes.

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Further, providing number of resources and services will not be the indication of the effective utilization of the library materials, hence users require skills and knowledge to exploit the resources of the library to the fullest. These skills and knowledge are provided by a well-planned and executed user education programme. This programme will impact skills and knowledge required to use the library resources independently and appropriately.

Educating a user is very essential for the successful functioning of any system which is new or complex. According to Aina (2004), Library processes could be so complex that an average user may not easily comprehend. Today a modern library is such a system which demands suitable user education programme for its users. According to Wilson (1980), user education programme is the process whereby potential users of information or those concerned with the creation of national information policies, are made aware of the value of information in specialized fields of activity and in everyday life, are instilled to use with positive attitude towards the need to seek information, and are motivated to use or develop information resources.

Reitz (2004) averred that user education includes “all the activities involved in teaching user how to make the best possible use of library resources, services and facilities, including formal and informal instruction delivered by a librarian or other staff member one- on one or in a group. Also includes online tutorials, audio-visual materials, and printed guides and pathfinders. In view of Mews (1980), users education programme as that topic as the instruction given to readers to help them make the best use of a library.” Malt (1990) states that “user education programme can be seen as a major strand within a “study skills” programme equipping the trainees with the knowledge and abilities to use libraries and information effectively and confidently; a skill of inestimable and enduring value. While Wajid (1998), opined that user education programme is that facet of library service, which is concerned with educating the library users in efficient use of library resources so that they are able to exploit them to the best of their advantage.

UNESCO (1998), states the user education programme as any effort which will guide and instruct existing and potential users, individually or collectively with objective of facilitating:

- i. The recognition of their own information needs:
- ii. The formalization of their needs:
- iii. The effective and efficient use of information service: as well as

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iv. The assessment of these services.

The analysis of the above definitions brings out the fact that any instruction or programme of information provided by libraries to users enables them to make more efficient and independent use of library resources and services. In a broad sense, the objective in giving user education is to help the user make the best use of the overall library resources. A carefully planned and robust user education programme greatly ensures the realization of this objective. Imam (2008), listed the specific aims of the programme to include:

- To enable the library user to make effective use of the resources available.
- To create awareness of print and non print materials available in the users discipline.
- To contribute to the personal and intellectual development of the user after his/her career.
- To provide the library user with the capacity of researching any problem.
- To enable the library user to use the varied information sources to solve academic and professional problems.
- To make the library user independent in accessing the library materials.

Why User Education?

It is based on the assumption that to know how to use a library is an essential part of the education to prepare the community for the continuous process of self education once the formal education is completed. Edem and Lawal(1996), posited that there is need for user education programme in our institution library because most libraries face the problem of information explosions as well as profuse scholarly publications couple with the fact that the average library users are desirous of retrieving information materials accurately within the shortest period of time, they further asserted that one of the ways of stimulating the active use of books, journals, audio-visual, e-resources and other material stored in libraries is by teaching the library users education programme to library users. In highlighting the importance of users education programme, Dadize (2009), stated that some fresh students entering colleges, polytechnics and university have limited knowledge of fundamental research and information competency skill and may not have learned how to locate information or how to use it in the original work and give proper credit for the information use.

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Libraries should thus be involved in teaching user education programme to guide and enable users to improve their information literacy skills.

Aina (2004), observes that information is expanding at a fast rate, resulting in information explosion and new resources are being introduced into the library. With the advent of information and communication technologies, which has penetrated almost all the activities of many libraries, it is important to explain the working of a library to a new user in detail. The ultimate objective is to enable users exploit the resource and services of a library to the fullest. For users to be aware of, and exploit effectively the resources and services of the library, they need to be competent in library use skills such exercise enables the librarian to orient the library users to the various, service facilities and professional personnel of the library.

Cuming (1990), opined that to learn how to use a library and to acquire interested love of reading are important elements of user education. There are a number of educational and library environments which necessitate user education programme service for effective utilization of the library resources, services and facilities namely;

- i. Quantitative growth of information
- ii. Growth in the number of inter-disciplinary and multi-disciplinary courses
- iii. Artificiality in the library system
- iv. Revolutionary changes in the physical forms of documents.
- v. Limited fiscal resources and
- vi. The emphasis on self study.

Thus library users require help to make sufficient use of all the library resources, services and facilities available for their use. It is therefore the libraries responsibility to ensure that the use of its information 6 sources, resources and services are maximized to benefit its users, hence the necessity for user education programme.

Goals and Objectives of User Education

In considering the goals and objectives for library user education programme, one becomes aware that, if expressed at all, these tend to be very vague. Thus Luban(1974), stated that several local developed guidelines for instruction in library use skills have been drawn up, but these guidelines are rarely based on basic objectives. Similarly, Stevenson (1977), has made the statement that “few libraries have expressed either the aims or objectives for user instruction”.

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The goals and objectives for library user education programmes must be in agreement with the aims and goals of the parent body to which the library is attached. The ultimate goals and objectives of user education programmes are:

- i. A general orientation or initiation for the users to available resources, services and facilities
- ii. The teaching of basic research skills and strategies: and
- iii. Instruction regarding the organization of literature and reference tools in various disciplines.

Facets of User Education Programme

The library user education programmes consist of the following interrelated components depending on each library's perception and experience:

- User Awareness
- Library Orientation
- Bibliographic Instruction
- Interest Profiling
- Library Skills
- Information Literacy
- Library Use Instruction.

Methods and Media of User Education Programme

A number of methods are available for impacting user education programmes in libraries. A single method may not be suitable for effective and perfect instruction. Hence it is suggested that a combination of method may be adopted based on the type of the user population and objective of the programme content. The methods of user the education programme can be categorized in to direct method and indirect methods. The direct methods are:

- i. Library instruction programme organized as part of the institution's general studies programme.
- ii. An informal meeting at educational or cultural function.
- iii. Library orientation, a series of lectures on library activities and conducted library tour.
- iv. Library user educations bibliographic instruction organized as examinable courses to be taken by all fresh students.
- v. Reader librarian dialogue while rendering reference service.

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The indirect methods include:

- i. Library guides
- ii. Circulation of documents list
- iii. Display
- iv. Directional signs
- v. Library handbook

The Significance of User Education Programme

Properly designed and meticulously executed user education programme are intended to ensure the effective utilization of the library resources, services and facilities by the users. Through the user education programme, the user is able to get any information he/she desires as well as developing the skills to use the resources, services and facilities of the library independently (Aina, 2004). The integration of ICT in almost all the activities of many libraries, it is important to explain the workings of a library to a new user in detail. User education is very necessary to promote a full exploitation of the library's resources, services, facilities including the human resources. Some of the benefits of user education programme are as identified below:

- i. It enables the library to raise the capacities of users to make use of literature and information resources or to improve the information consciousness of the library user.
- ii. It exposes the user to the organizational structure of the library, thus enhancing effective use of the library.
- iii. Better understanding of the library rule, and regulations governing the conduct of activities in the library
- iv. Users become familiarized with techniques and method of use of the library and retrieval of information.
- v. The user education programme will inculcate in the users the life-long habit of self-discovery and learning through effective library use.
- vi. It helps to save the librarians and the users' time. It is the library's responsibility to ensure that the use of its resources, services, and facilities are maximized to benefit of users, hence, the necessity for robust user education programmes.

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User education programme, for all intent and purpose, is an important factor in ensuring effective utilization of library resources even though the programme is faced with a lot of challenges which include.

- i. Absence of well developed curricula that will help the teaching of user education programme
- ii. Lack of funds for library user education programme implementation
- iii. Over dependence on one is a two hours tour of the library by new users during the week of their general orientation
- iv. The use of unqualified personnel to teach the user education programme
- v. Faculty resistance to collaborate with librarians in teaching user education programme
- vi. Inadequate library staff to cope with the amount of work involved
- vii. Lack of time for teaching and practical work.
- viii. Inadequate information resources for learning.

It must be noted that these impediments enumerated above require concerted effort on the part of the librarian, if the full role of our libraries is to be appreciated and its resources effectively utilized.

To solve these problems, Livehabura (1999), is of the opinion that the user education programme should be integrated within the curriculum so that the contents and coverage of the programme accommodates information development, learning and research. Joseph (2005) asserts on the need for an explicit statement of objectives, availability of infrastructure, qualified trainers, careful choice of teaching methods and regular systematic evaluation of the programme. According to Onifade (2011), the programme should be review to reflect users' needs in the aspect of electronic resources modern trends in information literacy. To arrest these myriads of problems bedeviling user education programme ,Akinloye (1992) averred that no single approach can be adopted to solve these problems. Rather a carefully designed and faithfully implemented user education programme will quicken the effort of user in retrieving and effectively utilizing the library resources, services and facilities.

Conclusion

New library members coming first time in the library have difficulties and certain confusion, as a result, they cannot use the library resources, services and facilities exhaustively and expeditiously. Library user education programme encompasses all

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types of activities designed to teach new users about library services, facilities, organization, resources, and search strategies in order to equip them with the basic skills and knowledge to enable them to make effective, optimal, efficient and independent use of information resources and services available in the library. Okon (2008) stated that if users cannot retrieve and utilize the available materials and services due to lack of possessing library skills, the huge investment on cost of materials, staff, building and energy would become wasted.

For the maximum exploitation of library resources, services and facilities by users, the librarian must provide appropriate user education programmes to library users. In view of the crucial roles of user's education programmes towards effective utilization of library resources, the following suggestions are necessary for considerations;

- i. The need of restructuring the programme is to reflect user's needs in the aspect of electronic resource modern trends in information literacy
- ii. Systematic evaluation of the process of the user education programme should be an essential aspect of user education.
- iii. Availability of a written policy framework to guide user education programme
- iv. Libraries should increase the number of employees' expert and skillful librarian who can provide user education programme.
- v. Libraries should make the user education programme compulsory for all users and provide them with instructional materials.
- vi. The programme should be allocated reasonable time, so as to enable practical aspect taught effectively.
- vii. The librarian should incorporate the use of audio-visuals and other media to show how to use library facilities, such as the catalogue and reference materials.
- viii. Less reliance on one day crash programme called a library orientation as it can never be a replacement for user education programme.
- ix. Introduction of a workable policy by the government that would see to it that the students are introduced to user education programme right from the nursery and primary school will greatly enhance the programme.

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